

INFLUENCE OF PPARG2 POLYMORPHISM IN THE PRO12Ala GENE ON THE RISK OF PURULENT-NECROTIC DAMAGE TO THE LEGS IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES

Kh.T. Musashaykhov¹, I.R. Nazarov²

Andijan State Medical Institute^{1,2}

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Abstract. *This study was conducted on patients undergoing inpatient treatment at the clinical bases of the Andijan State Medical Institute. To implement the goals and objectives of our scientific research, a total of 201 people were involved in the research. Molecular genetic studies were conducted at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

It can be seen that the Pro12Ala polymorphism of the PPARG2 gene has a statistically significant tendency to cause purulent-necrotic diseases of the lower extremities in the group of patients with diabetes mellitus, i.e., the probability of developing these pathologies is 4.9 times higher in patients with the unfavorable Ala/Ala genotype ($\chi^2=2.5$; OR=4.9; 95%CI:0.69-35.25).

Statistical processing of the results was carried out using the standard OpenEpi V.9.2. software package.

Keywords: *mutation, genetic marker PPARG2, diabetes mellitus, diabetic ankle, necrosis.*

Introduction. Purulent-necrotic lesions of the foot tissues in a patient with diabetes mellitus are a serious complication, leading to severe consequences: from high amputation of the lower limb to the patient's death. At the same time, there is a growing trend in the number of patients with diabetic foot syndrome, whose share in Russia is 4-10% and in the USA- 3-8% of all patients with diabetes [1, 2].

Diabetes mellitus leads among all diseases in Russia, with about 8 million people suffering from it, often being one of the main causes of early disability and mortality of working-age patients. It is precisely patients diagnosed with DM who develop diabetic foot syndrome. The frequency of DFS is 20-80% of the total number of patients with DM [4,5,7]. In recent decades, the frequency of DM detection has increased significantly. The number of identified patients with diabetes mellitus increases by 5-7% every year. According to experts from the World Health Organization (WHO), the incidence of DM doubles every 10-15 years, and by 2025, 250 million people will be diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus [8,10,11]. In patients diagnosed with DM, compared to the general population, the likelihood of complications occurring is 10-15 times higher.

"For medications for one diabetes patient, approximately \$3.5 thousand per year is needed." Purulent-necrotic changes in the foot occur in 15-20% of patients with diabetes mellitus. One of the reasons for the formation of DFS in this group of patients is genetic mutations [3,6,9].

Research material and methods. To implement the goals and objectives of our scientific research, a total of 201 people were involved in the research. The diagnosis of diabetes mellitus (DM) and purulent-necrotic diseases of the lower extremities (PND) was carried out in accordance with currently accepted clinical recommendations. Based on the data of the recommended clinical

classification, 2 subgroups were formed from 103 patients of the main group involved in the observation process: 1 group - 58 patients with diabetes mellitus and purulent-necrotic diseases of the lower extremities; 2nd group - 45 patients with DM, but without purulent-necrotic diseases of the lower extremities.

The comparison group consisted of 98 conditionally healthy individuals.

As material for the control sample, genomic DNA preparations were used, which correspond to the sex and age of patients in the study group independently isolated from "conditionally healthy" individuals who did not have clinical signs of the above pathologies in themselves and close relatives, and are stored in the DNA bank of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The median age of patients in the main group was 60.3 ± 1.0 years, which indicates the predominance of the adult category. For comparison, the average age of the participants in the control group, consisting of "conditionally healthy" individuals, was 58.3 ± 3.9 years.

Mutation testing was carried out on a Rotor-Gene Q (Quagen, Germany) device using a commercial test kit from "Sintol" LLC (Russia).

Statistical processing of the results was performed using the standard OpenEpi V.9.2 application software package.

Obtained results and their discussion.

When analyzing the duration of DM, which is a background disease, it was found that the majority of patients (49.5%) had this disease for more than 7 years. This led to a high risk of complications in other organs. This data indicates a direct correlation between the duration of DM and circulatory disorders in the peripheral arterial system, which subsequently leads to the transition to the stage of decompensation. Accordingly, the shorter the duration of the disease, the fewer vascular complications were observed.

Often, patients were admitted to our surgical department after unsuccessful attempts at inpatient and outpatient treatment in other medical institutions. Most of them have undergone two or more surgical interventions. It should be noted that in 74.1% of patients, OICH lasted more than two weeks. This circumstance served as the basis for their inclusion in the group with a high risk of developing complications in the postoperative period.

1 patient with a purulent inflammatory process spreading to the lower leg underwent emergency surgery. In this case, a gilotin amputation of the lower leg was performed above the pathological focus, followed by a planned secondary amputation with removal of some muscles and myoplasty in the upper third of the lower leg, forming a supporting stump.

In 58 (56.9%) patients, the course of DM was severe, accompanied by clinical signs of complications against the background of organic changes in target organs and systems. Despite the ongoing treatment aimed at improving the condition of the affected organs, it became necessary to conduct appropriate preoperative preparation and a special approach in the postoperative period for these patients.

According to the results of our study, no significant difference was found between the frequency of distribution of alleles of the Pro12Ala polymorphism of the PPARG2 gene in patients of the main group (wild Pro allele 83.0%; unfavorable Ala allele 17.0%) and in the comparison group (wild Pro allele 86.2%; unfavorable Ala allele 13.8%) ($\chi^2 < 3.84$; $p > 0.05$) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Frequency of distribution of alleles of the genetic marker PPARG2 (Pro12Ala) in the group of patients and control.

In the comparative analysis presented in Table 1, the functionally positive Pro/Pro genotype of the Pro12Ala polymorphism of the PPARG2 gene was less common in the main group of patients, i.e., 73 (70.9%) out of 103 patients, 72 (73.5%) out of 98 in the healthy group, however, the differences were statistically insignificant ($\chi^2 < 3.84$; $p > 0.05$) (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparative analysis of the prevalence of alleles and genotypes of the Pro12Ala polymorphism of the PPARG2 gene in samples of the main group and the comparison group.

Alleles and genotypes	Number of tested alleles and genotypes				χ^2	p	OR	95%CI
	Main group		Comparison group					
	n	%	n	%				
Pro	171	83.0	169	86.2	0.8	0.40	0.8	0.45 - 1.35
Ala	35	17.0	27	13.8	0.8	0.40	1.3	0.74 - 2.21
Pro/Pro	73	70.9	72	73.5	0.2	0.70	0.9	0.47 - 1.63
Pro/Ala	25	24.3	25	25.5	0.0	0.90	0.9	0.49 - 1.77
Ala/Ala	5	4.9	1	1.0	2.5	0.20	4.9	0.69 - 35.25

Also, in the main group of patients, the heterozygous Pro/Ala genotype was significantly less frequent than in the comparison group (24.3%), while in the group of relatively healthy individuals, this indicator was 25.5%, respectively ($\chi^2 = 0.0$; OR=0.9; 95%CI:0.49 - 1.77) (Table 1).

According to the analysis of the prevalence of genotypes in our groups, it was found that the proportion of patients carrying the unfavorable homozygous genotype Ala/Ala in the main group was slightly higher than in the control group, i.e., 4.9%, and this genotype in our comparison group was 1.0%, respectively. However, despite the insignificant differences, we can see that when determining the above genotype, there is a statistical tendency to cause purulent-necrotic diseases of the lower extremities in the group of patients with DM, that is, the probability of developing these pathologies is 4.9 times higher in patients with the unfavorable Ala/Ala genotype ($\chi^2 = 2.5$; OR=4.9; 95%CI:0.69-35.25) (Table 1).

Conclusion. Thus, the differences identified in our study in the distribution of the frequency of unfavorable Ala/Ala genotypes of the Pro12Ala polymorphism of the PPARG2 gene in the main group of patients and the group of healthy individuals showed a correlation between this homozygous genotype and the risk of progression of the studied pathologies.

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